

Preserving the *gotong royong* character for Indonesian Gen-Z in the digital era

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ABSTRACT

Gotong royong is a significant character for Indonesian generation Z (Gen-Z), based on traditional values, to unite this multicultural nation. However, the rapid development of digital media has the potential to alter traditional values. Gen-Z has the ability to quickly adapt to this technology. However, there is a concern that the *gotong royong* character may decline with the rise of digital media. This research investigates the perception of Gen-Z towards the *gotong royong* character and explores the way to preserve this value. This is qualitative descriptive research, whose population is made up of 108 students from six excellent schools in three Indonesian cities with different religious backgrounds and educational systems. The results show that Gen-Z still considers the *gotong royong* value is important. However, they also acknowledge that it can be threatened by the advancement of digital technology. With this awareness, Gen-Z can explore ways to adopt digital technology to preserve this character value, such as utilizing digital learning in club study and digital fundraising. This research recommends optimizing the school institution to take a more active role in fostering character through online character-building learning.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Gotong royong is a traditional value in Indonesia, which is widely recognized as a strong bond and a defining characteristic of the nation [1]. It embodies the spirit of togetherness and cooperation among citizens [2], allowing them to unite as one national identity despite differences in ethnicity, race, and religion. The first President of Indonesia, referred to the country as a nation of *gotong royong* [3], and this concept is known internationally for promoting the spirit of cooperation, collaboration, empathy for the weak, and the willingness to help others.

However, the advent of communication media and digital technology has the potential to influence or shift the development of good traditional values, including *gotong royong*, in the community [4]. Meanwhile, Generation Z (Gen-Z) is considered to be most easily adaptable and influenced by the development of digital technology [5]. In this regard, the development of technology has brought about more complex social changes, technology makes it difficult to explain social changes with certainty [6]. Furthermore, digital technology is feared to erode the value of *gotong royong* [7].

The importance of this discussion on the value of *gotong royong* is underscored by a survey on character building among students in Indonesia. This survey, which was conducted by the Ministry of Religious Affairs, explored five dimensions of character building, they include religiosity, nationalism, self-reliance, *gotong royong*, and integrity. The results showed that for three consecutive years, *gotong royong* consistently ranked as the second-lowest dimension after self-reliance. In contrast, nationalism and religiosity consistently ranked the highest, followed by integrity [8]–[10].

It is important to note that discussions about *gotong royong* in international publications are not extensive, and this is likely due to the fact that the term is uniquely Indonesian. Additionally, according to the calculations by VOS viewer on December 1st, 2022, only 63 scientific documents have been published on this topic, with most of them related to themes such as sustainable development, local wisdom, education, and business processes. These themes are similar to those found in discussions of cooperation, collaboration, and collectivism.

The literature on *gotong royong* can be categorized into several themes. First, this character is viewed as a unique value and identity of the Indonesian nation [11]–[14]. Second, it is considered in terms of practical aspects of community life in Indonesia [15]–[17]. Third, it is explored in the context of education [18]–[21], and fourth, *gotong royong* is discussed in relation to the challenges of social change [22]–[24].

According to the Indonesian great dictionary, *gotong royong* means cooperation or mutual assistance among members of a community [25]. Accordingly, Koentjaraningrat [26] stated that there are two forms of *gotong royong* in Indonesian. The first is mutual assistance, which is commonly seen in agricultural and household activities, celebrations, and in the events of disasters or death [24]. The second form is work cooperation. Work cooperation activities are usually carried out for the common interest of the community such as the improvement of roads and irrigation systems [15].

The value of character *gotong royong* identified as i) reflecting the action of valuing the spirit of cooperation and working together to solve problems; ii) establishing communication and friendship; iii) providing assistance/help to those in need; iv) showing respect to others and possessing the ability to work together, be inclusive, commit to joint decisions, and engage in mutual discussion and assistance; v) having empathy and solidarity, encouraging anti-discrimination, anti-violence, and voluntarism [18]. In this context, educational institutions have generated several ideas to educate the community at large on the values of *gotong royong*. These efforts were carried out to strengthen local social institutions that still rely on togetherness, uphold morals or ethics, honesty, and trust as a gateway to revitalizing this culture [27]. The implementation of this character in education can also take the form of developing instruments for assessment [28].

Therefore, the aim of this research is to examine the perceptions and appreciation of Gen-Z in Indonesia towards the *gotong royong* character amid the development of digital communication technology. This is particularly important considering the fact that Gen-Z currently lives in the era of digital communication technology, which provides various conveniences. On the other hand, the COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2022) has led to the creation of various forms of communication and transaction mediums that increasingly rely on digital technology, which is used on a daily basis. The increasingly indulgent life provided by digital technology may, admittedly, threaten the value of *gotong royong*, as a traditional character and value that has become the nation's defining characteristic [22].

This research is beneficial to the formulation of any values or behaviors required to ensure that *gotong royong* can still exist in the community. Knowledge about this value is important, especially amid technological ease, which tends to push the community towards individualism and egoism. Lastly, this research is also aimed at formulating factors that should be considered by families, schools, and the community while developing this character in the context of the advancement of digital technology.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The objective of this research was to investigate the perceptions and experiences of Indonesian Gen-Z regarding the value of *gotong royong* and the roles of school, family, and the community in developing this value, as well as their hopes for its development in the digital era. To achieve this objective, a mixed method approach was employed, consisting of both quantitative descriptive and qualitative approaches. Furthermore, the aim was to analyze the elements or values that constitute the *gotong royong* character of Gen-Z in the digital era.

The data used in this research were collected from six selected high schools located in three major Indonesian cities, namely Yogyakarta, Bandung, and Serang, as seen in Table 1. The six selected schools were not only excellent in academic performance but were also popular among students in their respective cities. These schools were selected based on the consideration that they were already excellent and on the fact that they had made a lot of efforts toward developing digital literacy. The data types collected were primary data consisting of opinions from students, and secondary data, which comprises information related to each theme.

Table 1. Research sample

Province	School name	Numbers of respondents
Banten	State <i>Madrasa Aliyah</i> Insan Cendekia Serpong	18
	Vocational High School Istana Mulia Serang	18
West Java	Christian Vocational High School Penabur Bandung	18
	State Senior High School 3 Bandung	18
Yogyakarta	State <i>Madrasa Aliyah</i> I Yogyakarta	18
	Industrial Technology Vocational High School Yogyakarta	18
Total respondents		108

Accordingly, a total of 18 students were selected from each school, with six students from each of the three levels of high school education. The selection process was carried out by the counseling teacher, who chose students that were considered to have a good understanding of values in character formation. Also, the majority of students were willing to participate in the questionnaire filling. Furthermore, the identification of the most contributing aspect in shaping *gotong royong* was based on the variation of answers and the number of students who agreed with each answer. Scores were given to each level of answer to measure their contribution, and then, the total weight of each answer was determined by summing all of the scores as shown in Table 2. Following this, the data presentation system was structured based on a constructivist context to illustrate the concept and development of the *gotong royong* character comprehensively for Gen-Z. The data was organized into complementary conceptual frameworks and the presentation was supported by several tables and illustrations of activities that showcased the involvement of Gen-Z in developing the *gotong royong* character.

Table 2. Scoring of respondents' answers

The order of answers	Score
1	7
2	6
3	5
4	4
5	3
6	2
7	1

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. *Gotong royong* amidst the advancement of digital technology

The estimated number of individuals that makes up Gen-Z in Indonesia is approximately 60 million, or about 20% of the total population. *Gotong royong* is a traditional value recognized as part of the national character [1], [14]. However, this value faces a challenge due to the immersion of this generation in digital media technology. A survey conducted on this subject indicates that Gen-Z in Indonesia recognizes that the existence of the value of *gotong royong* is threatened amidst the current development of digital technology.

Accordingly, there are several potential threats to the formation of the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z amidst the development of digital media. Based on a survey, as seen in Table 3, that converted the most frequently voiced opinions into factors, these threats include gaming (525), lack of socialization (412), not participating in organizations (420), social media addiction (378), showing off (370), wrong association (368), and other factors (91). According to student opinions, the factors that pose the most significant threat to the development of Gen-Z's communal character are as: i) gaming; ii) not participating in organizations; iii) not socializing; iv) social media addiction; v) showing off; vi) wrong association; and vii) other factors.

The development of digital technology, which brings about the provision of various digital games, is the biggest threat to the development of the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z. Gaming can hinder the development of social skills in children, causing them to become individualistic, unsociable, and unwilling to participate in organizations. The *gotong royong* character requires the presence of others, and thus, its development necessitates the existence of social groups. Being trapped in the fascination of games alone is dangerous for the development of this character.

Therefore, in order to reestablish an understanding and awareness of this value, Gen-Z needs to socialize. One way to achieve this is by involving them in social organizations or communities. The second most significant threat is not participating in organizations. Failing to know about organizations leads to a lack of comprehension regarding the collective norms of communal life. Therefore, Gen-Z needs to be introduced to organizations at an early age, so they can understand their rights and obligations as members of an organization.

Table 3. Activities that threaten the *gotong royong* character according to Gen-Z in Indonesia

	Gaming		Not participating in organization		Not socialized		Showing off		Wrong association		Others	
	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv
	37	259	12	84	4	28	10	70	11	77	3	21
	16	96	15	90	24	144	13	78	8	48	1	6
	20	100	20	100	18	90	11	55	15	75	1	5
	9	36	20	80	14	56	23	92	17	68	0	0
	5	15	14	42	22	66	16	48	25	75	2	6
	8	16	11	22	13	26	12	24	10	20	3	6
	3	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	5	5	47	47
	98	525	94	420	97	412	88	370	91	368	57	91

N=The number of respondents; Conv=Conversion Score

3.2. Constructing character through the *gotong royong* values

Furthermore, this research revealed that Gen-Z still recognizes several important values required to develop the *gotong royong* character. The field data, which involved 108 students, were collected to identify the most contributing aspect that shapes the character of togetherness. As presented in Table 4, respondents provided varying answers to each question, and the number of respondents (N) for each aspect is as: collaboration (527), cooperation (430), communication (394), mutual help (476), empathy (435), joint action (294), and other factors (105).

Table 4. Aspects of the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z

Collaboration		Mutual help		Empathy		Cooperation		Communication		Others	
N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv
37	259	11	77	10	70	15	105	15	105	5	35
22	132	32	192	15	90	11	66	4	24	1	6
12	60	15	75	26	130	18	90	17	85	1	5
10	40	18	72	19	76	24	96	19	76	1	4
5	15	15	45	13	39	18	54	25	75	1	3
7	14	7	14	14	28	7	14	14	28	1	2
7	7	1	1	2	2	5	5	1	1	50	50
100	527	99	476	99	435	98	430	95	394	60	105

N=The number of respondents; Conv=Conversion score

The data shows that Gen-Z in Indonesia is cognizant of the significance of values, such as collaboration, mutual aid, cooperation, empathy, communication, and togetherness in maintaining the *gotong royong* character. In order to instill these values, it is essential to cultivate them in schools, families, and communities. Schools, being the primary educational institutions where students spend most of their time, is a crucial pillar in nurturing these values.

Additionally, to develop the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z, the primary element required is collaboration. In order to appropriately foster this character, the generation firstly needs to have a community. This community can take various forms such as study groups, interest groups, youth organizations in the local area, and community organizations such as neighborhood associations. These groups can assist in comprehending the problems experienced by other individuals or groups, creating concern for the social environment, fostering motivation to help others, fighting for shared values/interests, and organizing shared interests.

Constructively, to realize the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z, a circle community must be established, where communication, empathy, mutual help, cooperation, and collaboration are developed. From the ideas that emerged, several forms of activities are required, they include small communities, educational processes, shared agendas, active organizing, and social sanctions. It is also important to note that apart from values and agreements, social sanctions are also necessary for those who violate the rules [29]. As the future generation, Gen-Z needs to be educated and provided with sanctions, at least a warning, if they do not meet the requirements of socializing.

3.3. Three strategic environments for shaping the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z

Three environments are commonly recognized as strategic for shaping students' character, they include the family, school, and community [30]. Among these three environments, the family is considered the most influential, given its dominant role in determining the final values of student character [31]. However, in the context of the digital era, for Gen-Z, the role of each environment has evolved, with fieldwork now assuming a critical role in character development.

3.3.1. School environment

According to field data, numerous school activities contribute to the development of the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z. Table 5 shows that the activities include studying together (573), participating in social service activities (466), visiting friends in distress (422), fulfilling class duties (436), organizing fundraising and social events (405), as well as other activities (162). In addition to the aforementioned activities, respondents have also identified other actions that can foster the *gotong royong* character in Generation Z, such as engaging in community service, offering support to friends in need, organizing activities, joining competition teams, supporting teammates during competitions, participating in class evaluations, becoming members of school organizations, attending orientation sessions focused on cooperation, receiving guidance from teachers, participating in social action, and paying group dues.

Table 5. School activities for forming the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z

Studying together		Class duty		Visiting friend		Social activities		Helping others		Others	
N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv
47	329	9	63	7	49	4	28	19	133	5	35
23	138	26	156	12	72	11	66	21	126	0	0
10	50	17	85	25	125	30	150	12	60	1	5
5	20	13	52	31	124	22	88	19	76	3	12
8	24	24	72	15	45	23	69	21	63	4	12
6	12	4	8	3	6	2	4	4	8	49	98
0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
99	573	93	436	94	422	92	405	96	466	62	162

N=The number of respondents; Conv=Conversion score

Accordingly, the abundance of activities in the school environment underscores the importance of the organizers' initiative in developing the *gotong royong* character of Gen Z. According to respondents, the school environment is important primarily because the students' ages are relatively similar. Such a setting allows for social interactions among students in groups, enabling them to assume various roles and develop conflict resolution skills, both of which are prerequisites for the moral character development of individuals [18], [29]. Unlike at home, where a sense of togetherness may be imposed by parents, the sense of togetherness in the school environment is more organic.

3.3.2. Family environment

The family environment is widely recognized as the most influential factor in shaping a child's character [31]. Even though the external environment such as school and community has provided valuable lessons on good character traits, without the affirmation of these same values in the family, the results can be reversed. Role models in the family, usually the older members (parents, older siblings), play a crucial role in guiding the younger generation to develop positive values in themselves.

According to respondents, the most influential activities in developing the *gotong royong* character in the family, include i) helping with household chores; ii) dividing household duties and assigning responsibilities; iii) praying together; iv) eating together; v) helping others and neighbors; and vi) other activities as indicated in Table 6. Admittedly, the *gotong royong* character is formed in families when children have the awareness and willingness to help complete household tasks. Other factors in the family or home that also contribute to the development of the *gotong royong* character, include sharing, going on vacations together, assisting each other within the family, doing household chores together, participating in family events, holding discussions, and making out time to gather together.

Table 6. Family environment activities forming the *Gotong royong* character in Gen-Z

Family task		Helping Home Job		Praying together		Eating together		Social Service		Other	
N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv
23	161	20	140	23	161	13	91	8	56	5	35
16	96	34	204	19	114	15	90	9	54	2	12
26	130	12	60	22	110	12	60	22	110	1	5
19	76	20	80	20	80	20	80	15	60	1	4
7	21	10	30	7	21	27	81	40	120	3	9
9	18	0	0	3	6	3	6	2	4	51	102
1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
101	503	96	514	95	493	90	408	96	404	63	167

N=The number of respondents; Conv=Conversion Score

3.3.3. Community environment

Activities in the community are significant contributors to the development of the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z. Both the community at large and educational institutions play a vital role in shaping the character of this generation [32]. Accordingly, the obtained field data indicated that the most significant activities in the community that contribute to the proper development of the *gotong royong* character are voluntary work (544), social fundraising (443), national commemoration days (439), collaborations with organizations (405), social service (382), community Wi-Fi provision (251), among other activities (97), as seen in Table 7. It is important to note that voluntary work and social service are distinguished here. Voluntary work involves working together to solve community problems, such as cleaning the streets, gutters, or public facilities, while social service entails working together to help those in need or distress. The data shows that Gen-Z's involvement in voluntary work activities helps them to understand the *gotong royong* character better. Furthermore, other activities that contribute to the development of *gotong royong* include joint meetings among residents, helping those who are grieving, nighttime surveillance to ensure neighborhood security, sharing food, getting to know each other, participating in sports, eating together, and visiting sick neighbors.

Table 7. Community environment activities forming the *Gotong royong* character in Gen-Z

Community service		Social fund		Memorial national day		Follow organization		Social action		Wi-Fi community		Other	
N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv	N	Conv
54	378	5	35	8	56	9	63	5	35	7	49	4	28
13	78	21	126	23	138	11	66	18	108	6	36	1	6
8	40	26	130	27	135	20	100	9	45	2	10	1	5
6	24	22	88	18	72	23	92	22	88	1	4	1	4
2	6	19	57	9	27	23	69	32	96	5	15	2	6
5	10	3	6	5	10	6	12	4	8	66	132	2	4
8	8	1	1	1	1	3	3	2	2	5	5	44	44
96	544	97	443	91	439	95	405	92	382	92	251	55	97

N=The number of respondents; Conv=Conversion score

In response to this problem, young people who are part of a community are seen as the starting point for the formation of the *gotong royong* character among Gen-Z. To develop this awareness, it is essential to have positive groups both in schools and in the wider community. This involves creating positive circles or communities that allow for sharing of issues, roles, and responsibilities.

In addition to being part of an organization, it is also important for Gen-Z to make the most of the advancements in communication technology [32]. This can help reduce the risk of individuals getting lost in online games or social media, and instead assist them in channeling their energies toward more productive and collaborative activities. Accordingly, in order to create positive circles or communities, younger generations need to receive guidance from senior members of the community. This can be in the form of both self-formed groups among Gen-Z, as well as groups created by schools or the wider community.

To promote a sense of community among Gen-Z, it is important to provide positive examples and content through social media campaigns that promote collaboration and *gotong royong* [33], [34]. It is also essential for young people to associate themselves with positive influences, understand and respect cultural and social values, participate in supportive communities, promote fairness and justice, attend webinars, and be active in social media groups. Thus, the community exerts a positive influence on the development of *gotong royong* among Gen-Z individuals.

3.4. Learning circle and digital funding: *gotong royong* in the digital technology era

The advancement of digital technology has brought about both convenience and threats to some positive traditional values. However, the development of this technology is inevitable. It is, thus, essential to embrace digital technology positively and anticipate any negative effects that may arise. *Gotong royong*, as mentioned in various literature, can take the form of crowdfunding [35], collaborative online learning [36], and other digital innovations, such as digital fundraising, which has the potential to preserve social capital and cooperation [37], [38].

Specifically, schools offer the most potential environment for developing the *gotong royong* character among Gen-Z. Some reasons why schools are more likely to succeed is that they are more open to utilizing digital-based learning more widely [39] and can act as protectors, models, and mentors [40]. The full-day learning model is also effective in character development [41]. In contrast, families primarily focus more on respect and the goal of maintaining the parents' values, and this can help in shaping the *gotong royong* character.

It is important to note that the Indonesian community sometimes lacks literacy in digital media development for character building. Therefore, by encouraging students to work together in groups, they will become aware of their strengths and weaknesses and positive competition between them can help achieve optimal learning achievements. By being active, creative, independent, and responsible, students can improve their motivation and self-confidence [42]–[44]. In the case of Christian Education Board Vocational High School Penabur Bandung, an appropriate approach is necessary to develop the *gotong royong* character among the school's many ethnic Chinese students in Bandung. One way is to introduce multiethnic society to student through citizenship education [45].

Following this, in the context of the digital era, the strategic role of the school environment is to promote collaborative learning groups that rely on digital media technology [46]. In this regard, Harison emphasized the significance of two essential components for character development in the digital era, namely character teachers and online character reinforcement facilitators [47]. One of the most notable practices that reflect this spirit is the existence of WhatsApp groups for study and collaborative learning, which are supported by character teachers via online platforms. These groups allow students to remind each other of tasks, share responsibilities, and utilize digital media to complete their assignments. Moreover, the digital circle community can be an attractive medium for developing the *gotong royong* character. To strengthen this character within the community, various communication models and personal approaches can be employed, which constitutes a significant challenge for Gen-Z given their increased immersion in gaming and gadgets [48].

The formation of project learning teams within the digital circle community of schools can effectively enhance students' character and life skills [49]. Every year, students in life skills groups are required to create projects related to the life skills they are pursuing. These projects are necessary, because they aid the students in building certain character traits, such as honesty. During this project period, the students are asked to create teams and plans for activities to be carried out, which will later be reported as a source of assessment for the team's success.

Subsequently, positive social media circle communities can assume different forms, including study, hobby, and social care groups. These digital circle communities provide an effective means of addressing the potential threat of student alienation caused by the lure of gaming and social media. Some students have expressed the need for spaces/activities provided by environments that are open to their participation, indicating their desire to participate in existing social groups, but are unsure where to start and are apprehensive about the views of those who have already participated.

With the presence of a digital community, the process of digital education on the value of *gotong royong* can be developed. This form of education is crucial in leveraging digital communication technology to strengthen character. One way to accomplish this is by disseminating content, podcasts, infographics, vlogs, and posters that highlight the importance of *gotong royong*. With adequate information about its importance, Gen-Z will in turn recognize and consider it important. Moreover, this character, according to the founding fathers of the nation, is the core value of Pancasila.

In addition to digital education, another activity model of *gotong royong* for Gen-Z is to carry out social actions together through digital technology. An example of this was when students raised funds to help the victims of the landslide disaster that occurred at Cjanjur in 2022 by utilizing digital communication for charity and social fundraising activities. Today, platforms like kitabisa.com have made it easier to raise any amount of funds to help those in need. Such social activities can foster empathy and a willingness to help others [24].

Following this, another positive activity that promotes *gotong royong* is collaboration in creating digital works. Gen-Z is a generation with many innovative ideas and a desire to showcase their work [50]. In this regard, technological advancements have made it easier for young people to collaborate in creating digital content, such as short films, podcasts, and reports. Going forward, utilizing digital technology in developing the *gotong royong* character can include, developing educative content on *gotong royong* through digital media, forming positive digital community circles, carrying out social actions together through digital media; and creating digital works together. Practically, several important activities that can facilitate the development of the *gotong royong* character using digital media include creating content for social activities, sharing content with others, creating TikTok videos or Twitter threads for fundraising, creating works (films, animations, advertisements, short films, podcasts or comics, campaigns, news about natural disasters, learning together) that depict togetherness, creating online volunteering activities (such as free teaching, online donations, motivational content, online competitions, webinars, social media hashtag movements), and so on.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research suggests that the advancement of digital technology in the field of information has raised concerns regarding the potential threat to the development of the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z. However, it also shows that this generation, in Indonesia, still considers the concept of

this character to be important. Hence, the progress of digital media is expected to facilitate the interests of the generation toward the preservation of the *gotong royong* character. Moreover, the research reveals that the use of digital technology in the context of maintaining the *gotong royong* character is evident through the spontaneous activism carried out by students during a social disaster. This finding indicates that students are still moved to raise social funds for disaster victims by utilizing the progress of social media.

Furthermore, this research concludes that the formation of the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z is based on various activities and core values such as collaboration, teamwork, communication, mutual assistance, and empathy. Interestingly, Gen-Z is also aware of things that have the potential to damage this character, such as i) gaming, which is the biggest potential threat to the formation of *gotong royong* character, as students become isolated from their communities; ii) not participating in the organization, which causes students to have difficulty building cooperation with others; iii) being antisocial or selfish; iv) being addicted to social media, as well as; v) showing off and selecting the wrong associations.

In order to develop these core values in the digital era, the role of three educational environments, namely family, school, and the community, is considered very important. Although the family is instrumental in shaping student character, this research suggests that in the context of digital technology advancement, it is not solely reliant on the family's role. Institutions outside the family, such as schools, have the most opportunity to develop the *gotong royong* character in Gen-Z. However, many parents in Indonesia still have insufficient knowledge of digital communication, and in many ways, lag behind in their children's ability to understand digital systems. Therefore, in the digital context, this research recommends that schools play a more significant role in developing Gen-Z's *gotong royong* character using digital media.

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